

Reproducible Key Performance Indicator (KPI) Measurement Experiments in 6G Networks under Mobility Conditions

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Abstract—6G networks are expected to support a wide variety of use cases from different vertical sectors with stringent requirements in terms of different key performance indicators (KPIs). As new experimental testbeds are being deployed to demonstrate and evaluate new technologies, it is important to perform systematic and reproducible experiments for measuring the relevant KPIs. However, there is a lack of tools for automated KPI measurement in mobility scenarios, which is specially relevant to analyze dynamic behaviors, such as handover events. In this paper, we address this gap with the proposal and implementation of a new tool to automate KPI measurement experiments from the terminal-side under programmable mobility scenarios. Our experimental results, validated on the 6G-SANDBOX's Málaga platform, demonstrate the potential of our solution for achieving reproducibility in KPI measurement experiments under mobility conditions.

Index Terms—6G, Handover, Key Performance Indicator (KPI) Measurement Experiments, Mobility, Reproducibility.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reproducible experiments are essential across all disciplines to ensure results can be validated, replicated, and compared effectively. Research in mobile networks is no exception, as it demands thorough testing. While reproducibility is more straightforward when proposals are evaluated using mathematical models or simulations, experimental evaluations are a critical step before deployment. These evaluations help identifying practical implementation challenges, deployment constraints, and model inaccuracies that simulations cannot identify [1].

Achieving reproducibility in experimental evaluations is challenging due to various uncontrollable factors such as environmental conditions and inherent randomness. Although recent efforts have introduced reproducible testbeds for mobile network experimentation [2]–[4], they are mostly focused on static scenarios, neglecting mobility. However, this is an essential aspect for assessing performance under dynamic user behavior, such as handovers.

In our previous work on seamless MEC migration in highly dynamic environments [5], we experimentally analyzed handovers using a methodology that involved a user equipment (UE) mounted in a car controlled remotely by a human operator. Nevertheless, this approach posed significant challenges for systematic reproducibility, since the car was manually controlled by a human in every iteration.

Thus, in this work we introduce a new tool for executing reproducible-mobility experiments in next-generation networks. Our proposal is based on a UE with programmable accurate mobility which can capture end-to-end key performance indicators (KPIs) and radio related metrics, generating time-series datasets with location and KPI information.

The main contribution of this work is the design, development and validation of a KPI measurement tool to execute reproducible mobility experiments. We integrated this tool into the Málaga testbed platform offered by the 6G-SANDBOX project. The experimental results highlight the tool's capability to evaluate network performance, contributing to the advancement of reproducible experimentation in the emerging field of 6G networks.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

As the move towards sixth generation (6G) networks takes place, a significant improvement in the performance and efficiency of wireless communications is expected. One of the key elements for standardization is the performance in mobility scenarios, which is particularly challenging. Network KPIs, such as latency, throughput or packet loss, are significantly sensitive to variations in network conditions and movement patterns of UEs.

Currently, there is a lack of tools and methodologies capable of accurately measuring and analyzing KPIs in reproducible-mobility scenarios, as the solutions implemented to date are not designed to study network behavior in dynamic contexts.

Consequently, there is an absence of publicly available datasets with location information and KPI values. This hampers network assessment capabilities, as well as the development of predictive models and optimization tools for 6G networks.

We consider a mobile network scenario, such as the 5G represented in Fig. 1, in which different base stations provide wireless coverage to a set of UEs in a given area. The base stations are connected to the core network through a backhaul network. Each UE in the coverage area will attach to a base station to have access to data services. As each UE moves, the received signal strength from the different base stations will change and handover procedures may take place, forcing a change in the serving base station.

In this scenario, our goal is to have a comprehensive tool for the measurement and analysis of KPIs in which a UE can execute reproducible mobility experiments. The proposed solution must satisfy the following requirements:

- It must allow a UE to perform accurate and reproducible mobility patterns in controlled environments.
- It must capture radio-related metrics for signal strength indications and cell ID of the serving base station.
- It must capture detailed end-to-end performance metrics, such as throughput, latency and jitter.
- It must generate datasets that include time series of KPIs along with location information for analysis and decision making for 6G network deployments.

Fig. 1. Overview of a generic 5G network architecture.

The ultimate goal of the tool is to derive valuable insights for the design of future 6G networks, with a particular emphasis on handover events. To achieve this, given a mobility pattern to be executed repeatedly, this tool must be able to generate a set of time-series datasets containing representative measurements, both end-to-end network-layer KPIs and also radio-related metrics.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

This section details our proposed solution to address the challenges identified in the previous section, combining programmable hardware, specialized software and the generation of detailed datasets.

A. Hardware Architecture

The proposed hardware architecture combines different commercial modules with both general and specialized functions to jointly address programmable mobility and the capture of network metrics. Through their integration, a physical

solution for the development of the proposed experiments is achieved. The following subsections describe the hardware components used, as well as their communication interfaces and the final integrated system developed.

The hardware architecture of the system combines multiple components to meet mobility, connectivity, and data processing requirements. At its core, it utilizes Marvelmind Robotics' indoor positioning system, featuring Super-Beacons for precise location tracking with ultrasound technology, and a Modem HW v5.1 for centralized control and communication. The Starter Set Super-MP-3D integrates these elements, achieving an accuracy around 2 cm, ideal for autonomous navigation using trilateration and precise clock synchronization.

Key devices include the Boxie 2 autonomous mobile robot from MarvelMind Robotics [6], equipped with different sensors, such as LIDARs and odometers for obstacle detection and path precision, and a Quectel RM510Q-GL 5G modem for high-speed wireless connectivity [7]. The Raspberry Pi 5 serves as the central processing unit, managing hardware and mobility, while a Xiaomi power-bank provides portable power. This configuration ensures robust performance for experimental environments.

Fig. 2. System hardware architecture.

Fig. 2 depicts a diagram with the hardware architecture of the system. The primary module is the Boxie 2, responsible for autonomous and reproducible movement across various scenarios. The Raspberry Pi 5 is mounted on top of the Boxie as the core component of the processing unit, powered by a power-bank. The Raspberry is connected via a serial port to the HW Modem v5.1 and the Quectel RM510Q-GL, which are also powered through the same connection. Fig. 3 shows a front view of the proposed autonomous tool, integrating all the components of the hardware architecture.

In addition, four Marvelmind's super-beacons are placed at fixed locations within the developed architecture for each

Fig. 3. Autonomous tool

scenario. These beacons communicate with the HW Modem through their integrated radio modules, collectively forming the Marvelmind Indoor Positioning System.

B. Software Architecture

This section outlines the software design created to enable autonomous movement, configure the UE device for network connectivity and capture real-time performance metrics. Figure 4 shows the software architecture developed to establish communications and capture network measurements. Note that besides the hardware architecture of our proposed tool, we also consider a virtual machine serving as an endpoint for the end-to-end network experiments.

Fig. 4. Software architecture.

The entire process begins with the initial configuration of the system to create the `wan0` interface on the Raspberry Pi and enable its connection to the 5G network. Once this setup is complete, the predefined waypoints defining the path of the experiment are transmitted through the serial port. After these waypoints are sent, the system captures the position of the robot and initiates the network performance tests.

To analyze network performance during mobility tests, different key metrics are examined through a variety of tools to assess the quality, strength, and stability of the connection. These metrics provide detailed insights into the behavior of the 5G network under different conditions, such as movement,

handovers, and varying signal coverage. Two types of metrics have been captured: radio-related KPIs and end-to-end network-layer KPIs.

On the one hand, the radio-related metrics focus on both signal strength and quality indicators. These measurements are obtained using `mbimcli` and by using an AT command executed through the `mmcli` utility. In detail, we consider the following metrics:

- Received signal strength indicator (RSSI), which measures the power level of the received signal, providing a basic indication of signal strength.
- Reference signal received power (RSRP), which offers a more accurate measurement by focusing on the power of the reference signals in LTE and 5G networks.
- Reference signal received quality (RSRQ), which quantifies signal quality by considering both signal strength and interference.
- Cell ID, which identifies the specific base station which the UE is using to access the network. This is essential for detecting handovers, as changes in the Cell ID can indicate when the device switches from one base station to another, enabling the monitoring of handover occurrences during mobility tests and allowing them to be correlated with other events and changes in KPIs.

On the other hand, the end-to-end network KPIs analyze the end-user performance. We consider the following metrics:

- Throughput: Amount of data successfully delivered through the network in a given amount of time. We consider both UDP and TCP throughput.
- Latency: Time taken for a packet to travel from the source to the destination through the network.
- Packet loss: Ratio of packets which have been sent but did not arrive at the destination.

These end-to-end network metrics are measured using the tools such as `fping` and `iperf`. The former is utilized to measure latency and packet loss by sending multiple ICMP echo requests to the virtual machine and measuring the round-trip time when the corresponding ICMP replies are received. On the other hand, `iperf` is used to measure uplink network throughput, supporting both TCP and UDP protocols to analyze throughput, jitter, and packet loss under varying traffic conditions. These tests are performed in the uplink direction, with the modem acting as the client and the virtual machine acting as the server.

During each experiment, our proposed tool leverages the Marvelmind positioning system to obtain real-time location information using X, Y, Z Cartesian coordinates, which are recorded in a common dataset with the signal quality metrics. These values, along with latency and packet loss data from `fping`, are temporarily stored in memory until the experiment concludes. At that point, the script safely stops the positioning system, terminates the network tests, and processes all collected data. The resulting information, including signal metrics, positioning data, and network performance results, is saved into comma-separated value (CSV) files for further

analysis, ensuring a reliable and consistent network evaluation under a reproducible mobility path (i.e., the same set of predefined waypoints).

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the results of the experiments carried out to validate our proposed solution. The experiments were conducted at the Málaga platform provided by the 6G-SANDBOX project [8], which offers an experimental beyond 5G (B5G) network, with different core network and various sets of base stations. For our experiments we used the micro cell base stations operating in the FR1 frequency band, which provide coverage to relatively large areas with enhanced indoor penetration. Fig. 5 shows the cell areas and physical cell identities (PCIs) of the Málaga platform, where the tests have been executed. We used a 5G core network implementation provided by Open5GS [9].

Fig. 5. Cell areas and PCIs on the Málaga platform.

In this scenario we conducted different experiments, involving indoor and outdoor locations, different mobility patterns (such as random waypoints and rectangular shapes) and different ICMP packet sizes and UDP bandwidths. The collected datasets with the results from these experiments have been made publicly available in Zenodo [10]. In this section, we focus our analysis on a specific experiment with the aim of analyzing the reproducibility capabilities offered by the proposed tool.

A. Reproducibility

Fig. 6 shows the environment where mobility tests have been conducted for the outdoor experiment with a rectangular shape mobility pattern. The predefined path for the tool has been highlighted in blue and the starting point marked as a circle. This setup has been carefully selected to ensure the repeated execution of handover operations by the modem between different base stations deployed in the area, specifically cells 0 and 1.

To manage the Marvelmind Indoor Positioning System, four Super-Beacons were strategically placed: two on the walls, one on a chair, and another on a tool cart (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Scenario and mobility pattern for the outdoor rectangular shape experiment.

This arrangement ensures accurate tracking and positioning throughout the testing area.

Once the map and mobility waypoints are configured, the Dashboard interface appears as shown in Figure 7. By placing a waypoint at each corner, the Boxie 2 repeatedly follows rectangular mobility patterns, during which systematic cell handovers take place.

Fig. 7. Dashboard view after configuration for the outdoor rectangular shape.

In the outdoor environment, the Málaga platform provides coverage through a series of base stations forming two cells: Cell 1 and Cell 3. Continuous handover occurs between these cells depending on the position of the UE. This behavior is depicted in Fig. 8, where the movement starts parallel to the wall with an initial connection to Cell 1. At the corner where the robot begins to approach the wall, a handover is executed to Cell 3. Subsequently, at the corner where the robot begins to move away from the wall, a second handover occurs to Cell 1.

Comparing the results obtained in both laps, reveals a high degree of reproducibility in the recorded Cell ID (see Fig. 8) and RSSI values (see Fig. 9), with notable consistency across most measurements. In both laps, the observed Cell IDs remain consistent, indicating that the device maintains connections with the same cells at key points along the route. This behavior suggests stability in cell allocation throughout the area covered

(a) First lap

(b) Second lap

Fig. 8. Cell ID for the outdoor rectangular shape mobility pattern.

by the experiment. In terms of RSSI value, we can observe minor fluctuations in both scenarios, which reveals the impact of environmental factors, such as temporary interferences or fluctuations in transmission power. Nevertheless, the main behavior remains consistent in both laps, showing low RSSI values when the handover is about to take place, and higher RSSI values after the handover event took place.

Fig. 10 shows a comparison of the trajectory followed by the robot (decomposed into X and Y coordinates) over time, for each of the two laps. The data from each of the laps is superimposed on each figure, allowing for a direct comparison of the robot's spatial movements. While the trajectories exhibit a high degree of similarity, reflecting the robot's consistent navigation path across laps, slight deviations can be observed at specific points. Notably, some outlier values appear at moments likely corresponding to the robot's repositioning or realignment, which could momentarily affect its recorded position. These

(a) First lap

(b) Second lap

Fig. 9. RSSI for the outdoor rectangular shape mobility pattern.

deviations may stem from transient adjustments in the robot's movement or slight delays in position tracking. Despite these localized anomalies, the overall alignment between the two trajectories reaffirms the reproducibility and robustness of the robot's navigation and the experimental conditions.

Fig. 11 shows the results of a throughput experiment for a UDP iperf with a bandwidth of 10 Mbps. After an initial transient stage, the figure shows a repeated pattern characterized by consistent and stable performance at 10 Mbps, followed by a sharp drop when the handover event takes place. After the handover is complete, there is a peak in throughput corresponding to the transmission of the packets that were queued during the handover, and subsequently the throughput stabilizes again at 10 Mbps. This result highlights the reproducibility of the experiment in terms of throughput for the different laps.

Overall, these results validate the reproducibility of our

(a) Comparison of X position in both laps

(b) Comparison of Y position in both laps

Fig. 10. Comparison of the path followed by the robot over time, for each of the two laps.

Fig. 11. Throughput (10 Mbps UDP iperf experiment) for the outdoor rectangular shape mobility pattern.

proposed programmable-mobility experiments. The analysis of the location, RSSI, and throughput shows a consistent behavior with minimal variations across the different laps of the experiment.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper we introduced a tool for automatically capturing location, end-to-end network KPIs and radio-related metrics in 6G deployments under mobility conditions. Our proposal integrated a robot with programmable mobility capabilities, with a Raspberry Pi and a 5G modem to provide cellular connectivity.

Our results, demonstrated that the proposed tool was able to seamlessly integrate with the experimental testbed provided by the Málaga platform of the 6G-SANDBOX. This integration did not involve any modification to the setup, showing its plug-and-play adaptability and interoperability with different deployment scenarios. We tested different deployments following simple mobility patterns, capturing radio-related metrics and end-to-end network-layer KPIs, along with location information. The reproducibility under mobility conditions has been showcased on a specific experiment involving two laps to the same path, revealing consistency in terms of location, RSSI and throughput across the two laps.

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